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Fri, Aug 4, 11:52 AM

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We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Edunesia: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan, "Islamic and Senior High Schools in School Market in Indonesia".

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Yth. Editor

Terima kasih atas review yang sangat bermanfaat. Manuskrif telah kami revisi dan disubmit via OJS. Semua perbaikan diberi highlight berwarna kuning.

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Thu, Sep 7, 6:25 AM

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